

Conducting Polyaniline : Dispersions, Nanoparticles and Nanocomposites^ψ

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After a brief introduction to conducting polymers and their processability problem, the synthesis of an economically attractive and environmentally stable conducting polymer, viz. polyaniline (PANI) in dispersion form (to overcome the processability problem) has been discussed. Nanoparticles of less than 20 nm diameter could be obtained from the particles in the dispersion by way of disintegrating them with the help of ultrasound. The nanoparticles produced *in situ* inside solutions of various matrix polymers undergo fractal aggregation. The nanocomposites obtained after removal of the solvent exhibit the fractally-grown self-ordered structure of the dispersed phase consisting of PANI when examined through a transmission electron microscope. The fractally-grown structure of the dispersed phase leads to reaching the percolation thresholds in the nanocomposites at extremely low PANI concentrations.

The search for materials with better and/or newer properties is never-ending. Polymers and inorganic semiconductors are the two major classes of materials with which the modern age can be identified. Polymers, of course, as commonly known and introduced in the early 30s, were known to be electrically non-conducting being built, as they are, of molecules with their bonding molecular orbitals all filled up which leads to filled-up valence band for the solid polymer separated from the empty conduction band by an energy barrier which is so large that it prevents the valence band electrons move into the conduction band by way of thermal excitation and help electrical conduction at reasonable temperatures.

Interestingly, it is this nonconducting property which enabled a considerable portion of the polymer industry to develop in the area of electrical insulation where the high resistivity, high dielectric breakdown strength and lower cost have been of prime importance.

Conducting polymers

The late 70s saw a remarkable development when it was discovered that polyacetylene (PA) which has an intrinsic conductivity (σ) in between that of a semiconductor and an insulator ($\sigma_{\text{cis PA}} \approx 1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) can be made highly conducting ($\sigma \approx 1 \times 10^3 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) by partial oxidation or reduction (Fig. 1)¹. The latter processes introduce charge

Fig. 1. Doping of polyacetylene.

carriers in the polymer chain and are called doping, a term borrowed from the field of inorganic semiconductors. The oxidation process which introduces positive charge in the

polymer backbone is called *p*-type doping and the reduction process which introduces negative charge is called *n*-type doping². Soon a host of other organic polymers with extended main-chain conjugation was prepared which on doping becomes conducting. Some of these organic conducting polymers are shown in Fig. 2.

Polymer	σ^a S/cm	Type of doping
 trans-polyacetylene	1.7×10^5	n, p
 Poly(p-phenylene)	1×10^3	n, p
 Polypyrrole	7.5×10^3	p
 Polythiophene	1×10^3	p
 Poly(p-phenylene vinylene)	5×10^3	p

Fig. 2. Some examples of conducting polymers : (a) maximum conductivity reported for the doped polymer.

The field of conducting polymers that thus emerged was deemed to hold considerable promise as because one sees here a combination of properties : the film-forming properties of the polymers and the electronic properties of semiconductors. Applications in various areas and devices

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are reported or envisaged^{3,4}. Some of these are : antistatics, electromagnetic/radiofrequency interference shielding, batteries, photovoltaic devices, sensors, electrocatalysis, corrosion protection of metals and semiconductors, photochromic and electrochromic devices etc. Amongst the latest developments may be mentioned the examples of the fabrication of all-plastics transistors⁵ and tunable polymeric LED devices which are suitable for large area displays^{6,7}. However, a severe constraint in the area of applications of these polymers stems from their general lack of solubility and fusibility. As would be evident from the structures of these materials (Fig. 2), the molecules are rather rigid and associated with high cohesive force. The solubility and fusibility have however been improved in some cases by suitable chemical modification of the polymer chains which process increases chain spacing and reduces the cohesive force. To cite some examples, poly(3-substituted-pyrroles)⁸, poly(3-substituted-thiophenes)⁹ and substituted-polyanilines¹⁰⁻¹³ which are soluble in sharp contrast to the unmodified polymers.

An alternative approach could be to prepare the polymers in colloidal dispersion form which then can be used either straight or blended with latexes or solutions of nonconducting polymers for various end-applications (and also from the viewpoint of economy of the products since the conducting polymers are rather expensive). Although the first dispersion made was that of polyacetylene¹⁴, most works are concerned with the preparation and utilization of only two polymers, viz. polypyrrole^{15,16} and polyaniline¹⁷⁻²¹, the reason being that these two polymers are very easily prepared by chemical oxidation of their respective monomers. The polymerization when carried out in the presence of certain soluble polymeric stabilizers yields the desired dispersions. By this process stable dispersions containing particles of various sizes (30 to 200 nm) depending on the combination of reagents and process conditions have been reported. It has been established by scanning tunneling microscopy that these particles, in fact, are compound particles being composed of particulates of 5–10 nm dia²². Subsequently, we observed that some of these particles can be disintegrated into particulates (< 20 nm) on the application of ultrasound²³. Furthermore, the particulates (nanoparticles) so prepared undergo self-assembly in various polymer matrices leading to blends with extremely low percolation threshold²³.

It may be mentioned here that nanomaterials occupy now the pride of place to the material scientists. By 'nano' one usually means materials in the size range of 1 to 100 nm. However, in the lower side of this range *ca.* 1–10 nm, materials exhibit electronic and optical properties which are different from those found when they are molecularly dispersed or macroscopically aggregated²⁴.

We shall discuss here the preparation of unstable nanoparticles (< 20 nm) of PANI which can be blended with a polymer solution. A blend film cast from the mixture shows the dispersed phase consisting of PANI

nanoparticles aggregated fractally to a self-ordered structure forming a network and the percolation threshold turns out to be extremely small.

Chemical method of polyaniline preparation

Polyaniline is prepared chemically by the oxidation of aniline using various oxidizing agents such as $S_2O_8^{2-}$, $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$, IO_3^- , Fe^{3+} etc.²⁵⁻²⁹. The reaction not only links the aniline molecules head-to-tail, but also oxidizes the product still further to produce polyaniline in which about 50% of the amino groups are converted to imino groups²⁶. This form of polyaniline is commonly known as emeraldine^{26,30}. A harmful side-reaction is the head-to-head coupling of two aniline molecules generating benzidine which is a strong carcinogen³¹. The benzidine problem is grave enough to threaten the acceptability of PANI as an electronic material³². The half-oxidized form of polyaniline, i.e. the emeraldine base (EB) shown in Fig. 3 is nonconducting. On treatment with a protonic acid it becomes converted into emeraldine salt in which every alter-

Fig. 3. Conducting and nonconducting forms of polyaniline.

nate NH unit is a radical cation³³⁻³⁷. In the terminology of solid state physics the radical ion charge carriers are called polarons. The emeraldine salt is the usual conducting form of PANI.

As regards the molecular weight it may be noted that a great deal of controversy exists since true molecular solutions of polyaniline are not unambiguously prepared which is an indication of the strong cohesive force operating between the molecules. Most attempts on molecular weight determination used the dedoped polyaniline (emeraldine base) and *N*-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) solvent along with lithium salts, the latter being added to decrease the intermolecular interaction between the molecules of PANI³⁷⁻⁴¹. However, Davied *et al.*⁴² argued that true solutions are not obtained even in NMP with 0.5% LiCl added and also this solvent dissolves only a part of EB and not the whole. They therefore used fully reduced form of emeraldine base (leucoemeraldine) for molecular weight determination

which, they claim, does not suffer from the abovementioned solubility problem. They determined $\bar{M}_n = 9900$ and $\bar{M}_w = 50700$ for PANI prepared by using ammonium persulfate (APS) oxidant (2.8 g aniline hydrochloride oxidized with 1.15 g APS in 1 M HCl at 1°)⁴².

Dispersion polymerization of aniline

The PANI prepared by the chemical oxidation process described above is obtained as a powdery precipitate. However, if a soluble polymer capable of being adsorbed or chemically grafted to PANI is also added to the polymerization reaction recipe, the PANI is obtained in the form of a colloidal dispersion. This method of preparing polymer dispersions by the use of a soluble polymeric stabilizer in the course of polymerization of a monomer is

TABLE 1—PREPARATION OF PANI DISPERSIONS IN ACIDIC (HCl) AQUEOUS (50%) ETHANOL^a AND THE CHARACTERIZATION OF PANI PARTICLES

Sl. no.	PVME used %	PANI characterization data				Particle size ^d nm
		PVME/PANI ^b	Cl/N ^c	(Cl + S)/N ^c	σ S cm ⁻¹	
1.	0.0	0	0.40	0.49	4.42	—
2.	0.50	0.08	0.41	0.51	3.74	195 ± 17(L) 124 ± 14(B)
3.	1.00	0.11	0.41	0.51	2.52	121 ± 22(L) 57 ± 20(B)
4.	1.50	0.14	0.41	0.51	2.35	—
5.	2.50	0.19	0.41	0.52	1.10	110 ± 28(L) 47 ± 21(B)

^a[An]/[APS] = 2; [An] = 0.180 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 2°; time = 2 h.

^bWeight ratio, calculated on the basis of reduced N content of the particles relative to pure polyaniline (Sl. no. 1). ^cAtom ratio. ^dL = length, B = maximum breadth; values are average of 50 measurements of oblong-shaped particles.

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called dispersion polymerization⁴³. In this process the polymer formed being insoluble in the medium, separates out from it forming what is known as nuclei. The latter having high surface free energy try to reduce it by adsorbing the stabilizer (or its grafted product) on their surface.

However, the ever present van der Waals attractive force between the nuclei also acts parallelly bringing about coalescence of the nuclei and their aggregates until a critical stage is reached where stable particles which do not undergo coalescence amongst themselves (homocoalescence) are formed. These particles have their surfaces well covered by the stabilizer molecules such that repulsion between the particles on account of the adsorbed stabilizer molecules exceeds the van der Waals attraction between them⁴⁴. This kind of stabilization is called steric stabilization⁴³⁻⁴⁵. The stability in this case will be unaffected by the ionic strength of the medium unlike the case of charge-stabilized colloids. Thus, PANI prepared by the dispersion polymerization of aniline is stable in a highly acidic

medium, e.g. 1 M HCl. The steric stabilization however will be lost when the medium is made a theta or a poor solvent for the polymeric stabilizer either by changing temperature or by adding other reagents⁴⁵.

The repulsive interaction between the stabilized particles arises principally from two sources : (i) volume restriction and (ii) osmotic effects^{43,45}. In the first case, there occurs loss of configurational entropy when the adsorbed polymer molecules face an impenetrable barrier when two stable particles with polymers adsorbed on their surface approach closer to each other. In the second case, as the particles approach closer to each other there will occur interpenetration of chain segments resulting in an increase in concentration of polymer in the space between the particles with a consequent increase in local osmotic pressure so that solvent would rush in and separate the particles.

As far as dispersion polymerization of aniline is concerned, the early attempts using conventional water-soluble polymeric stabilizers like poly(vinyl alcohol), methyl cellulose etc. turned out to be unsuccessful¹⁷. However, later work showed that stable dispersions of polyaniline can be prepared using the above stabilizers under appropriate reaction conditions²¹. Our work proved that poly(vinyl methyl ether) (PVME) is a very effective stabilizer for the dispersion polymerization of aniline and both water and aqueous alcohols may be used as polymerization media¹⁹. Table 1 reproduces the polymerization recipe and the characterization of PANI particles produced in 50% ethanol using various concentrations of PVME stabilizer at fixed concentration of aniline and APS. It will be seen from the data that the atomic ratio of (Cl + S)/N in the PANI formed is close to 0.5. The Cl and S atoms are due to the Cl⁻ and HSO₄⁻ ions which are present in PANI to compensate the positive charge in proton-doped PANI. It would be evident from Fig. 3 that emeraldine salt form of PANI should have the (Cl + S)/N ratio equal to 0.5, which is in close agreement with the above mentioned result. The conductivity of the product decreases with the increase in PVME (which is an insulator) incorporation in the particles. However, in view of the mechanism of stabilization in dispersion polymerization as discussed above, one would have expected the PANI particle surface to be covered uniformly with the nonconducting stabilizer molecules and hence the PANI particles should not have shown any conductivity at all. Furthermore, Armes *et al.*⁴⁶ calculated that in such particles the stabilizer layer should be about 2–5 nm thick if they are uniformly distributed over the particle surface. The thickness of the insulating stabilizer polymer layer is large enough to prevent conduction by charge tunneling mechanism⁴⁶. Subsequently, however, on examination of the dried particles using scanning tunneling microscopy, Armes *et al.*²³ concluded that the stabilizer chains redistribute over the particle surface during drying of the particles such that at the contact points between the particles no stabilizer molecules exist. Apart from this knowledge the scanning tunneling microscopy also

Fig. 4. Transmission electron micrographs of PANI.HCl colloid particles : (a) prior to sonication and (b) 1.5 h after sonication (Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23; copyright 1995 American Chemical Society).

revealed that the particles are in fact compound particles being composed of particulates of 5–10 nm size. This result is in conformity with the particle growth mechanism in dispersion polymerization discussed earlier in this presentation. It has been suggested that the particle growth takes place via absorption of the nuclei/particulates by the stable particles⁴⁴. However, since the polymer is semicrystalline and the polymerization temperature is below the glass transition temperature (T_g) the accreted nuclei/particulates would not mingle into a coherent mass but form a raspberry type internal structure for the particles. The particles are oblong in shape. The oblong character increases with increase in stabilizer concentration used in the synthesis as the L/B data given in the last column of Table 1 would reveal.

Nanoparticles of polyaniline

It would be evident from the data given in Table 1 that the sizes of the PANI particles cover the range of ~50 to 125 nm × 100 to 200 nm. However, one remarkable property of the particles is that they can be disintegrated into particles less than 20 nm when a suspension of the particles is placed in an ultrasonic bath²³. This is shown in Fig. 4. The disintegrated particles are now in the nano size range of interest for electronic application. It should be noted that the disintegration of the compound particles by the above process does not occur for all stabilizers. Also it has been our experience with PVME-stabilized particles that disintegration becomes increasingly difficult as the content of incorporated PVME increases²³. It may be noted that for particles produced in a dispersion polymerization not all the stabilizer molecules may be found on the surface of the particles, a part may be present inside the particles⁴⁷. This situation follows from the mechanism of particle growth discussed earlier in this presentation. The particle grows by absorbing the unstable nuclei/particulates. As the latter enters into a particle, the stabilizer should move from the surface of nuclei/particulate to the particle surface in order to stabilize the extra surface created in the latter following the absorption of the former. However, the kinetics of the process may not be fast enough for some stabilizers

so that a part of theirs may end up remaining inside the particles. Such stabilizer molecules which remain inside the particles act as a glue to hold together the particulates which constitute a particle. Greater the stabilizer content inside the particles, the greater will be the gluing action and more difficult it will be to disintegrate the particles.

Nanocomposites

Preparation :

Having produced the nanoparticles of polyaniline as described above we wanted to use them to prepare blends of conducting polyaniline with non-conducting polymers and examine the percolation threshold. For this purpose, all that was needed was to suspend the PVME-stabilized PANI particles in a polymer solution, sonicate the suspension for some time and then cast film. As because PVME is soluble both in water and many organic solvents, the present method of blending allows us to prepare blends with water-soluble polymers such as poly(vinyl alcohol) as well as with organo-soluble polymers²³. We describe below the results of our study on the morphology and the electrical properties of the blends of PANI with two polymers; the one water-soluble, e.g. PVA and the other organo-soluble, e.g. poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC).

Electrical properties :

A representative plot for the variation of conductivity of the blends with PANI concentration is shown in Fig. 5 where PVA was used as the matrix polymer. Fig. 5 does not show any well-defined percolation threshold. An estimate for the latter may be obtained from the figure by determining PANI concentration for which the specific conductivity (σ) of the blends assumes the value of $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. This latter value is considered to represent the insulator-semiconductor transition⁴⁸. However, a quantitative estimate of the percolation threshold (f_p) may be obtained by fitting the data used in Fig. 5 to the scaling law of percolation theory which reads as follows⁴⁹ :

$$\sigma = c(f - f_p)^t \quad (1)$$

where, c is a constant, t is the critical exponent, f the

volume fraction of the filler particles (here PANI) and f_p the volume fraction of the filler particles at percolation threshold. The fitting is shown in Fig. 6 which yields a value of 3.6×10^{-4} for f_p and 1.96 for t . Similar treatments of σ , f data for blends of PANI with other matrix polymers, yields f_p , t values for the corresponding blends which are

Fig. 5. Plot of log electrical conductivity vs PANI.HCl concentration in PANI.HCl-PVA blends films. The inset shows an enlarged view for the low PANI.HCl concentration region (Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23; copyright 1995 American Chemical Society).

Fig. 6. Plot of log conductivity vs log $(W - W_c)$, where W is the wt.% PANI.HCl in the blends and W_c refers the same at percolation threshold (Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23; copyright 1995 American Chemical Society).

shown in Table 2. The f_p values turn out to be unusually low for all systems, falling in the range of $(2 \text{ to } 4) \times 10^{-4}$,

i.e. 0.02 to 0.04 volume percent. This is in sharp contrast to the value of 0.16 (i.e. 16 volume percent) theoretically predicted for f_p by the percolation theory for conducting particles dispersed in an insulating matrix in three dimensions⁴⁹.

TABLE 2— f_p AND t DATA FOR VARIOUS BLENDS OF PANI.HCl WITH CONVENTIONAL POLYMERS

Matrix	$10^4 f_p$	t
PVC	4.02	1.87
PS	4.19	1.91
PVAc	3.18	1.94
PMMA	2.14	1.89
PVA	3.60	1.96

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Previously, using a solution blending method, where camphor sulphonic acid doped PANI (PANI.CSA) was the conducting component and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) was the nonconducting component, Heeger *et al.*^{50,51} reported a low f_p value ($f \approx 0.01$) which was attributed to the self-assembly of PANI.CSA molecules into a fibrillar network morphology during liquid-liquid phase separation which occurs on the evaporation of solvent from the solution of the blend. Subsequently, a further lower value of f_p , viz. $f_p = 3 \times 10^{-3}$ was reported by Heeger's group which was achieved by a change in molecular weight of the matrix polymer PMMA⁵². It may be noted here that for the C-black composites which were prepared using nanoparticles of carbon (semispherical hollow shells with a diameter of 30 nm) Michels *et al.*^{53,57} also reported a low f_p , viz. $f_p \approx 1 \times 10^{-3}$. However, in these systems the conductivity near f_p is of the order of $10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ which is two orders of magnitude less than the value found with our blends and 4 decades lower than the value reported by Heeger's group for PANI.CSA-PMMA blends at f_p . Coming to the value of t of equation (1), our experimental value 1.92 ± 0.05 (Table 2) is in agreement with that calculated from the percolation theory assuming an idealized fractal structure near the percolation threshold for the three-dimensional system.

Morphology :

In order to find out the origin of the extremely low percolation threshold in our PANI blends we studied the morphology development for the PANI dispersed phase in the blends with increasing PANI concentration. This was done by taking bright field images of the blend films directly cast over carbon coated copper grids of a transmission electron microscope. Parts a-e of Fig. 7 show the TEM images of the PANI-PVA blend films containing respectively 0.035, 0.045, 0.05 and 0.5 wt% of PANI²³. The images show a fibrillar morphology of the dispersed phase. At the lowest PANI loading of 0.035% the PANI nanoparticles are found to exist in isolated clusters (Fig.7a). On increasing PANI concentration to 0.045% the clusters appear to be weakly interconnected (Fig.7b) which indicates that

the system is near percolation. The structure is stringy and tenuous which is characteristic of clusters near percolation. As the PANI concentration is increased further to 0.05% the interconnection between clusters become more dense. TEM studies thus show that the percolation threshold is somewhere around 0.045% which is in very good agreement with the value determined from conductivity studies (Figs. 5 and 6).

On increasing the PANI concentration still further to 0.5%, the system is found to undergo self-organization generating a particular pattern for the network which is in the process of formation in Fig.7d (identified by the bold

impression in the figure) and nearly complete in Fig.7e. The self-ordering of the aggregation process helps to reach percolation at extremely low concentration of PANI in the blends. Similar self-assembly was noted for PANI.CSA molecules by Heeger *et al.*^{50,51} who reported a similar morphology as described above here for their PANI.CSA-PMMA blends cast from the solution of the blends in *m*-cresol which were prepared by sonicating PANI.CSA powders in a solution of PMMA for 48 h.

The morphology development for the PANI-PVC blends with increasing concentration of PANI is shown in parts a-d of Fig. 8⁵⁵. Unlike the PANI-PVA blends which

Fig. 7. Transmission electron micrographs of PANI.HCl-PVA blend films containing different amounts of PANI.HCl : (a) 0.035, (b) 0.045, (c) 0.05, (d) 0.5 and (e) 0.5 wt.%, the latter from a different area from the same film as was used for part (d) (Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23; copyright 1995 American Chemical Society).

Fig. 8. TEM images of PANI.HCl-PVC blend films containing different amounts of PANI.HCl : (a) 0.035, (b) 0.045, (c) 0.59, (d) 2.34 wt% (Reprinted from Ref. 55; copyright 1995 with kind permission from Elsevier Science S.A., P.O. Box 564, 1001 Lausanne, Switzerland).

Fig. 9. Enlarged TEM image of a globule of PANI in a 0.59% blend film of PANI.HCl-PVC (Reprinted from Ref. 55; copyright 1995 with kind permission from Elsevier Science S.A., P.O. Box 564, 1001 Lausanne, Switzerland).

exhibited a fibrillar morphology, the PANI-PVC blends exhibited a globular morphology. However, the globular PANI particles are found to be aggregated in a network structure above the percolation threshold. The change in morphology from fibrillar to globular that occurs on changing the matrix polymer from PVA to PVC may have its origin in the difference in thermodynamic interaction between PANI and PVA on one hand and PANI and PVC on the other.

Fig. 10. Log-log plot of area vs length of the structure shown in Fig. 7e.

Fractal structure of the dispersed phase :

Fig. 9 shows an exploded view of the globules forming the network shown in Fig. 8c. From this enlarged image it is evident that the globules themselves are networks of nanoparticles. Thus, the morphological features described above have the property of self-similarity, i.e. every part of

the structure has the same structural pattern as that of the whole. This is a characteristic of fractal objects which often have shapes and structures like dendrites^{56,57}. The main difference between an Euclidian and a fractal object is that the latter grows faster than the former, because not every point, which is defined by the Euclidian space is occupied in a fractal object. Another important property of the fractals is that their anisotropic growth leads to a self-ordering mechanism⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸. The mass of a fractal object is predicted to scale as L^D , where L is the size and D is the fractal or Hausdorff dimension which is typically less than the Euclidian dimension. The fractal dimension of the structure shown in Fig. 7e was measured in the following way^{59,60}. The area (S) occupied by the PANI aggregates was counted inside a series of squares with dimensions chosen on successively larger length scales. A log-log plot was then made of S vs the length of the enclosed square which yields a straight-line (Fig. 10), the slope of which gives the fractal dimension. In this way a value of 1.78 for the fractal dimension was determined for the structure shown in Fig. 7e.

It should be noted that unstable colloid particles commonly undergo aggregation to fractal structures⁶¹⁻⁶⁵ Weitz

Fig. 11. Schematic diagram for fractal aggregate formation in nanocomposites from the breakdown of PVME stabilized colloid particles of PANI.HCl.

and Oliveria studied the fractal dimension of the aggregates formed in destabilized gold sols by way of analysing transmission electron microscopic (TEM) images of the aggregates which were dried over TEM grids from the sol⁶². They found that the aggregates are scale invariant and the fractal dimensions were determined to be ~ 1.75 . They reasoned that although their analysis was performed for a two-dimensional projection of the clusters, the result should apply to the three-dimensional colloid clusters since fractal dimension remains unchanged upon projection provided it is ≤ 2 . It was pointed out that the value of $D \sim 1.75$ is in excellent agreement with the value predicted by computer simulations of diffusion-limited aggregation when the clusters themselves are allowed to aggregate^{66,67}.

The fractal aggregation of the nanoparticles of PANI seen in PANI blends with PVA or PVC suggests that the nanoparticles of PANI when generated from bigger but stable PANI particles by sonication are unstable since they do not have enough stabilizer molecules on their surface.

This follows from the mechanism of particle growth described earlier in this communication. The unstable nanoparticles therefore undergo aggregation to yield fractal structures featuring self-ordering. This anisotropic growth characteristic of fractal structures leads to network formation at very low concentrations of PANI in the blends. The situation may be schematically summarized as shown in Fig. 11.

The work presented here provides a simple method of producing nanoparticles of conducting polyaniline and shows that the nanoparticles produced *in situ* inside polymer solutions go on aggregating fractally to a self-ordered structure when solvents are removed from the dispersions to generate nanocomposites with extremely low percolation thresholds.

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